

Extremophile SOD in industrial applications

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Abstract:

The oxidation of proteins, DNA, lipids and other macromolecules that build up living cells is a chemical process triggered by an excess of free radicals or reactive oxygen species (ROS) that are produced by the cell metabolism. At moderate concentrations, the ROS participate in the cell physiological processes, whereas when they reach high levels, often due to factors such as cigarette smoke, ozone, ionizing radiation, heavy metals or UV radiation, they can alter the DNA structure and irreversibly modify proteins and lipids (Ayala et al., 2014). The superoxide anion (O_2^-) is the main free radical produced during oxidative stress conditions and can be converted by the enzyme SuperOxide Dismutase (SOD) into H_2O_2 , which is in turn transformed into H_2O and O_2 by the enzyme catalase. Thanks to their versatility, SODs may find interesting applications in different industrial sectors, including human health care, where these enzymes are essential for the prevention of neurodegenerative diseases, gastrointestinal pathologies and age-associated damages (Valgimigli et al., 2015). Nevertheless the employment of SODs in human health care and Pharmaceuticals present some limitations, primarily linked to their reduced stability and consequent rapid loss of efficacy. Extremophile bacteria, which proliferate in extreme physical and/or geochemical conditions, represent a source of stable SOD enzymes, able to function even in conditions of high or low temperature, in the presence of high UV doses, very basic or acidic pH. In the present study we have cloned and expressed three SOD genes of extremophile bacteria in *Lycopersicon esculentum* (tomato) cell cultures in order to produce extracts with extraordinary stability features for industrial applications. Indeed, plant cell cultures represent a competitive option for the expression of heterologous proteins, as the derived extracts, besides the recombinant proteins of interest, contain a wide variety of secondary metabolites with antioxidant and dermo-protective effects (Barbulova et al., 2014). Once enriched with the extremophile SODs, the tomato cell extracts have acquired unexpected properties of resistance to high UV doses, high temperature, low pH and elevated salt concentrations (Fig. 1), thus suitable to be developed as ingredients for different types of applications.

Keywords:

SuperOxide Dismutase; Reactive Oxygen Species; extremophile bacteria; plant cell cultures; protein expression; industrial applications.

Figure 1: Figure illustrating a native protein gel, stained for SOD enzymatic activity. The band intensity was quantified and the measures were reported as % values in the column graph below. WT: plant extract; DrSOD: plant extract containing the extremophile SOD; t=0: no UV exposure; t=7h: 7h exposure to UV radiation.

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Biography :

Dr. Fabio Apone graduated In Biology In 1994 and obtained his PhD title in Protistology (Biology of Unicellular Organisms) in 1998 at the University of Pisa, Italy. He worked for 3 years as Postdoc Researcher in Italy and at the University of California, San Diego, focusing on Cell Biology and signal transduction mechanisms. Later he was a research scientist at Arena Pharmaceuticals Inc, a Biotech Company located in San Diego, California, studying plant receptors for the discovery of novel agrochemicals. He is co-founder and Scientific Director of Arterra Bioscience (www.arterrabio.it), a young Biotech Company located in Napoli, Italy, focused on the identification and study of new active ingredients for different industrial applications. Since 2013, Dr. Fabio Apone has also been Scientific Coordinator and Administration Board member of Vitalab srl (www.vitalabactive.com), a joint-venture company involved in the development and commercialization of cosmetic active ingredients.

Innovation of cotton germplasm of draught- & salinity-tolerance

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Abstract:

Cotton, a kind of crops with strong draught- and salt-resistance, is important to explore excellent draught- or salt-tolerant genes and improve the level of draught- or salt-tolerance on cotton. The study was performed with *Gossypium hirsutum* cv ZhongH177 and Zhong9835 as the material, 12 genes of draught- or salinity-resistance were isolated from the mitochondria, which plays an essential role in draught- and salt-tolerance of plants. Based on 0.4% salt stress method, we obtained three salt-tolerance related gene *ccmC*, *rps12* and *nad3* from mitochondria of cotton. We cloned them from (*Gossypium hirsutum* L., a draught- and salt-tolerance variety). Subsequently, the analysis of biological information were used; subcellular localization of those genes were found out; based on over-expression vector, transformed into *Arabidopsis thaliana* by floral-dip method and transformed into cotton by gene gun transgenic technology. The over-expression vector pBI121-*rps12*, pBI121-*ccmC* and pBI121-*nad3* were constructed and transferred into cotton by gene gun transgenic technology, which laid a certain foundation for further analysis salt-tolerant molecular mechanism and salt resistance germplasm innovation of cotton.

Keywords:

Cotton, mitochondria, draught- and salt-tolerance, gene cloning, expression analysis

Biography :

Wuwei Ye, Ph.D., professor of cotton biology and genetics, associate head of Cotton Germplasm Department of Institute for Cotton Research, ICGI Co-Chair of Breeding & Applied Genomics Workgroup. Chinese Academy of Agricultural Sciences (ICR-CAAS), engages as a principal investigator (PI) in cotton genetics, applied genomics, and cotton breeding. As the group leader of the cotton germplasm identification, innovation and biodiversity research, I have focused my genetics, molecular genetics, and gene expression research on exploiting biotic and abiotic resistance of cotton germplasm for almost 30 years. I have participated in the cotton genome sequencing project, with the D, A and AD species of cotton. I have published 63 papers in *Nature Genetics*, *Nature Biotechnology*, *Plant Biotechnology Journal*, *BMC Genomics*, *BMC Genetics*, and *Molecular Genetics and Genomics* among other journals.

Out of Touch: Depletion of Mechanosensors Drives Wound-Healing and Cancer

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Abstract:

Since repeated tissue damage correlates with increased risk of cancer, there could be a correlation between tissue regeneration and cancer in that they involve growth in adult tissues. Indeed microRNA-21 levels are upregulated in both tissue regeneration and cancer. miRNA-21 causes depletion of several proteins but particularly, tropomyosin (Tpm) 2.1 depletion blocks rigidity sensing and causes growth on soft surfaces. In over forty cancer cell lines tested, at least 75% were missing major components of the rigidity sensing complex (about 60% had low Tpm 2.1). The rigidity sensing complex (about 2 μ m in length) contracts matrix adhesions by \sim 100nm; and if the force generated is greater than \sim 25 pN, then adhesions are reinforced and cells can grow (Wolfenson et al., 2016. Nat Cell Bio. 18:33). However, if the surface is soft and matrix force low, then the rigidity sensor in normal cells causes apoptosis by DAPK1 activation (Qin et al., 2018 BioRxiv. 320739). Transformed cancer cells lack rigidity-sensing contractions and grow on soft surfaces. Restoration of rigidity sensing in cancer cells by normalizing cytoskeletal protein levels (most often by restoring Tpm 2.1 levels) restores rigidity-dependent growth (Yang, B. et al., 2018 BioRxiv. 221176). Surprisingly, we find that cyclic mechanical stretch of transformed cancer cells activates apoptosis through calpain-dependent apoptosis. Restoring rigidity sensing in transformed cancer cells blocked stretch-induced apoptosis and caused rigidity-dependent growth (Tijore et al., 2018 BioRxiv. 491746). Conversely, normal cells become stretch-sensitive for apoptosis after transformation by depleting rigidity sensors through Tpm2.1 knockdown or knockdown of other tumor suppressor proteins needed for rigidity sensing. Thus, it seems that stretch sensitivity is a weakness of many cancer cell lines and this is related to the transformed cell state and not to the tissue type or other factors. Depletion of the rigidity mechanosensor to allow regenerative growth can lead to sustained loss of mechanosensing that enables cancerous growth.

Biography :

Hailing from Columbia University, Prof Michael Sheetz has more than 40 years' experience in the biomedical field. Introduced to Singapore by Prof Hew Choy Leong of the National University of Singapore's Department of Biological Sciences, Prof Sheetz was sought to lead an RCE project. This resulted in a two-year effort to organise and submit a proposal on Mechanobiology where Prof Sheetz set the theme and direction of the Mechanobiology Institute (MBI). As Executive Director of the MBI, he will be spending nine months a year in Singapore to oversee the Institute's programmes.

Genome-wide Quantitative Trait Loci Reveal the Genetic Basis of Cotton Fiber Quality and Yield-related Traits in a *G.hirsutum* RIL Population

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Abstract:

Cotton is widely cultivated globally because it provides natural fiber for the textile industry and human use. To identify quantitative trait loci (QTLs)/genes associated with fiber quality and yield, a recombinant inbred line (RIL) populations has been developed in upland cotton. A consensus map covering the whole genome was constructed with three types of markers (8295 markers, 5197.17 centimorgans (cM)). Six fiber yield and quality traits were evaluated in 17 environments, 983 QTLs were identified, and 198 of which were stable and mainly distributed on chromosomes 4, 6, 7, 13, 21, and 25. Thirty-seven QTL clusters were identified, in which 92.8% of paired traits with significant medium or high positive correlations had the same QTL additive effect directions, and all of the paired traits with significant medium or high negative correlations had opposite additive effect directions. A total of 1297 genes were found in the QTL cluster, of which 414 was expressed in two RNA-Seq data sets. A number of genes were discovered, 23 of which are promising candidate genes. Six important QTL clusters that included both fiber quality and yield traits were identified with opposite additive effect directions, and those on chromosome 13 (qClu-chr13-2) could increase fiber quality but reduce yield; this result was validated in a natural population using three markers. These data could provide information about the genetic basis of cotton fiber quality and yield and help cotton breeders to improve fiber quality and yield simultaneously.

Biography :

Professor Youlu Yuan is the Director of Biotechnology Research Department in Institute of Cotton Research, CAAS, based in Anyang, Henan, China. Professor Yuan has published over 100 papers on the subject of genome sequencing, genetic mapping, QTL identification, and molecular marker assisted selection about cotton fiber quality. He is a recognized expert in cotton excellent fiber quality variety. He has developed six cotton varieties: CCRI60, CCRI70, CCRI78, CCRI96, CCRI101 and CCRI112. After obtaining an Bachelor Degree in Agronomy from the Beijing Agricultural University in 1990, he started work on cotton hybrid variety development at Institute of Cotton Research, CAAS, China. Dr. Yuan started his work on Utilization of Dominant Glandless Strains in Cotton (*G.hirsutum* L.) for masrer degree of Agronomy in Nanjing Agricutiral University in 1994. In 2000 he obtained his ph.d. in Agronomy on Inheritance and Molecular Tagging of Fiber Quality Characters in Upland Cotton (*G.hirsuum* L.) with High Fiber Strength from the Nanjing g Agricultural University. He is currently a Visiting Professor in School of Agriculture Sciences of Zhengzhou University, and Visiting Professor in College of Agronomy of Xinjiang Agricultural University.